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Research Article

FORMULATION & EVALUATION OF MULTIPURPOSE TURMERIC CREAM

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The prepared herbal cream has best properties and having nutritional values using less chemical which protects the skin from the various skin problem. Since the cream was prepared by using simple ingredients and simple method so the cream is also economical. The herbal cosmetic formulation is safe to use and it can be used as the provision of a barrier to protect skin. The result of different tests of cream showed that the formation could be used topically in order to protect skin against damage. Natural remedies are more acceptable in the belief that they are safer with fewer side effects than the synthetic ones. Further research will carry out to check scientifically the synergistic action of formulation.

The cream was prepared by using the cream base that is bee's wax, liquid paraffin, borax, methylparaben, distilled water, Borax extracts of Turmeric,Neem and Tulsi. Homogenous mixing of all the excipients and the herbal extracts to formulate the cream, we have developed three batches of our herbal cream, namely F1H, F2H, and F3H. All three batches were evaluated for different parameters like appearance, PH, viscosity, phase separation.

Keywords: Herbal cream, Ideal Property, Formulation, Evaluation Test.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Medicinal or pharmaceutical chemistry is a branch of chemistry and pharmacology concerned with the design, synthesis, and development of pharmaceutical medications. Pharmaceutical chemistry focuses on the effectiveness of medications and the suitability of medical equipment for the uses for which it is intended.

Plant-derived substances and natural medicines have currently attracted super interest towards their flexible application, as medicinal plants are the richest supply of bioactive compounds utilized in traditional and modern medicinal drug. Herbal plant products are used as the foundation of numerous scientific treatments in human beings. herbal products are not only the most effective, but they are fantastically non- poisonous and have therapeutic doses properly underneath their toxic levels.

Cream is a semisolid emulsion that is mixture of oil and water, intended for application on the skin or mucus membrane. Creams are of two types namely oily creams and aqueous creams. The oily creams are w/o emulsion which are employed as emollients and cleansing agents. The aqueous creams are o/w emulsions These are useful as water washable bases. Herbal formulations always have attracted considerable attention because of their good activity and comparatively lesser or nil side effects with synthetic drug. Herbal cosmetics are defined as the beauty products which possess desirable physiological activity such as healing, smoothing appearance, enhancing and conditioning properties because of herbal ingredients.

Herbal Cream:

An cream including Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), and Tulsi (*Ocimum Sanctum Linn*) extract is being developed and evaluated in the current work.

Herbal cream have gained considerable attention in recent years due to their potential therapeutic properties and minimal side effects compared to synthetic counter parts. This project aims to provide an Multi purpose turmeric effect of the formulation and evaluation of herbal cream containing neem (*Azadirachta indica*), turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), and tulsi (*Ocimum tenuiflorum*).

Antioxidant Cream

That help to protect the skin surface from oxidative damage cause by Free radical an environmental aggressors like U.V and pollution. Antioxidant are often Found in skin care product formulas because of their powerful antiaging agent benefits.

Anti-Aging Cream:

Antiaging cream it helps the slow skin aging

process. aged skin Occur in youth new cells fail to replace the accumulation damaged new cells.

IDEAL PROPERTIES:

- Lightens dark spots
- Heal wounds
- Treats acne
- Turmeric for skin lightening

ADVANTAGES:

- Build collagen and helps in anti-aging.
- Decrease hyperpigmentation.
- Increase your natural glow.
- It's a potent anti-inflammatory and antioxidant.

DISADVANTAGES:

- Skin irritation or Dermatitis may occur due to the drug or excipient.
- May occur Burning, itching, stinging, or soreness.
- Flushed skin and inflammation.
- Not able to cure rapid sickness and accidents.
- Risk with self-dosing.

2. Literature Review:

1. Sailor Niyanta, *et.al.*, (2022)

Curcuma longa is also called as turmeric. Its zingiberaceae rhizomes are Used to make the spice. Curcumin is also known for its anti-inflammatory and Antioxidants qualities and skin protective characteristics. Curcumin is also treating Skin infections and inflammation in natural herbal medicine. The proposed of Project is to formulate turmeric based antioxidants cream. Different Physicochemical test was performed on turmeric Cream, including Spreadability, viscosity appearance, drug content homogeneity, pH Measurements. The study of finding various chemical property where determine to be satisfactory and consistent with the commercially available turmeric cream.

2. Kabanvera Estefania, *et.al.*, 2022

Turmeric Is a one of the most important spices. The main ingredients by turmeric Include curcumin, dimethoxy, and be dimethoxy. One of the pharmaceutical Preparations topical delivery systems is a cream preparation which is the solid Dosage form. Turmeric can be formulated in various preparation which is cream Dosage form. Advantage of cream preparation partial is that easy to wash and Clean. The evaluation test show that the formula produces a cream with yellow Color a characteristic order of turmeric and preparation with solid cream texture. And has homogeneity,

good dispersing ability.

3. Aim And Objective:

➤ **Aim:** Formulation and Evaluation of Multipurpose Turmeric Cream.

➤ **Objective:**

- It used as a Anti-inflammatory and Antioxidant.
- To study different evaluation parameter of formulation and their activities.
- Antioxidants can diminish the appearance of wrinkles and dark spots.
- To sun exposure and may reduce inflammation from sun damage.
- Curcumin Is the main active Ingredient in turmeric.

4. Plan of work:

Plan of Work for Formulation and Evaluation of Multipurpose Turmeric Cream:

STEP 1:

Literature Review:

Conduct a comprehensive literature review to gather information on herbs traditionally used in skincare and review scientific literature on their pharmacological properties.

STEP 2:

Selection of Drug:

- Neem
- Turmeric
- Tulsi

Neem plant is tropical evergreen trees to Indian subcontinent and easily available. It has been used in Ayurvedic medicine for more than 4000 years due to its medicinal properties. Most of the plant parts such as fruits, leaves, seeds, bark and root contain compound with proven antiseptic, antiviral, antipyretic, anti-inflammatory, antiulcer, antifungal etc.

STEP 3 :

Collection of Neem, Tulsi and Turmeric:

Leaves of AzadirachtaIndica (Neem) And Ocimumtenuiflorum(Tulsi) were collected from the tree in the college campus, rhizomes of curcuma longa were collected from different matured plant. The Leaves were wash by using distilled water and dry by using sun drying method.

STEP 4 :

Material And Method:

To formulate and evaluate a Multiple purpose turmeric cream, the materials required include herbal extracts/powders such as neem, turmeric, tulsian and borax, distilled water, liquid paraffin,

methyl paraben,rose water. The method involves selection

complementary herbs, preparing herbal extracts, melting the ingredients, mixing in the herbal extracts, And Preparing the Cream

STEP 5:

Instruments:

Weighing balance, ph Paper, Mixer, Hot plate, Measuring cylinder, Glass rod, Mixer/grinder, Conical flask, Morter and pestle.

STEP 6:

Evaluation Test:

- pH
- Colour
- Odour
- Teast
- Consistency

5. Drug profile:

1. Neem plant:

Fig No 1: Neem Plant

Synonym: Margosa, Neem tree, Azadirachtaindica, MeliaAzadirachta, Arishth, Nim tree

Biological source: Neem consists of almost all parts of the plants which are used as drug. Some important morphological parts are the dried stem bark, root bark, leaves and fruits of Azadirachtaindica also, known as Meliaazadirachta.

Family: Meliaceae

Geographical source: It is found in India, Pakistan, Shri Lanka, Malaya, Indonesia, Japan, tropical region of Australia an Africa. In India it is found in

Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamil Nādu, Rajasthan, MP.

Chemical Constituent:

1. Nimbin, 6- desacetylnimbinene.
2. Nimbinene, Nimbandiol, nimbolide.
3. Quercetin, β -sitosterol.
4. Ascorbic acid, n-hexacosanol, nonacosane and amino acid.

Uses:

- Nourishes Skin
- Treats Acne
- Neem has an anti-inflammatory property Help reduce acne
- Treated skin disease.

2. Turmeric Plant :

Fig No 2 : Turmeric Plant

Synonym: Curcuma longa, Curcuma domestica, Herbaceous plant, Genus curcuma, Seasoner Saffron, Indian Haladi, Curcumae

Family: Zingiberaceae

Biological source: Turmeric is the dried rhizome of curcuma longa Linn. Belonging to family zingiberaceae

Geographical source: They grow in warm, humid climates and thrive only in temperatures above 60°F (29.8°C). India, shri Lanka, the east Indies, Fiji, and Queensland (. Australia) all have climates that are conducive to growing turmeric.

Chemical constituents:

1. Curcuminoids- Non-volatile colouring matter.
2. Curcumin, a diferulomethane; desmethoxy dicinnarmoyl methane; bides methoxycurcumin.
3. Volatile oil:
 - a. l-cycloisoprenmyrcene
 - b. zinziberene,
 - c. turmerone,
 - d. a-atlantone,

Uses:

Turmeric is a versatile spice that has been used for centuries in various cultures for both culinary and medicinal purposes. Some of its common uses include:

1. Cooking: Turmeric is a key ingredient in many cuisines, particularly in Indian, Middle Eastern, and Southeast Asian cooking. It adds a vibrant yellow colour and a warm, slightly bitter flavour to dishes. It is commonly used in curries, soups, stews, rice dishes, and marinades.

Medicinal Purposes:

Turmeric has long been used in traditional medicine systems such as Ayurveda and Traditional Chinese Medicine for its potential health benefits. It contains a compound called curcumin, which is believed to have antioxidant, antiinflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. Some common medicinal uses of turmeric include:

- i. Ani-inflammatory properties
- ii. Ani-oxidant activity
- iii. Digestive Health
- iv. Immune system
- v. Skin Health

4. Tulsi Plant:

Fig No 3 : Tulsi Plant

Synonym: Holy basil, Tulasi

Family: Labiatae

Biological source: Tulsi consists of the fresh and dried leaves of Ocimum species like Ocimum sanctum L. and Ocimum basilicum L. etc. Tulsi consists of the fresh and dried leaves of Ocimum species like Ocimum sanctum L. and Ocimum basilicum L. etc.

Chemical constituent:

- 1) Linalol
- 2) Eugenol
- 3) Methylchavicol

- 4) Methylcinnamat
- 5) Linolen

Uses:

- 1) Ani-microbial
- 2) Ani-fungal
- 3) Stress relief
- 4) Antioxidant

6. Method and Material**1. Preparation of neem extract:**

After being carefully washed with distilled water, the plant leaves were picked and allowed to dry for 10 days in the shade. The powdered dry leaves were created. After being ingested for three hours with 350 ml of 90% ethanol, 100 g of powder was transferred to a percolator, and 150 ml of 90% ethanol was added. The powder was macerated for seven days while being stirred occasionally. After collecting and concentrating the ethanolic extract, a blackish-green residue was obtained. The extract was kept in a cool, dry location in an airtight

container.

Fig No 4: Extracted Neem

2. Preparation of Turmeric extract :

Dried rhizomes of turmeric was ground into a powder, and the extraction procedure was the same as it was for neem leaf extract. Plant extract with a ruby red hue was achieved and kept in an airtight container in a cool, dark location.

Fig No 5: Extracted Turmeric

3. Preparation of tulsi extract:

After being carefully washed with distilled water, the plant leaves were picked and allowed to dry for 10 days in the shade. The powdered dry leaves were created. After being ingested for three hours with 350 ml of 90% ethanol, 100 g of powder was transferred to a percolator, and 150 ml of 90% ethanol was added. The powder was macerated for seven days while being stirred occasionally. Formulation of cream

Table No 1: Formulation of Cream.

Sr. No	Ingredients	Formulation 1	Formulation 2	Formulation 3
1	Turmaric extract	2.5ml	1.8ml	1.7ml
2	Neem extract	2.5ml	2.3ml	2.7ml
3	Tulsi extract	1ml	1.3ml	1.5ml
4	Bees-wax	5.10gm	4.5gm	4.7gm
5	Liquid paraffine	18ml	20ml	20ml
6	Borax	0.50gm	0.60gm	0.65gm
7	Methyl paraben	0.30gm	0.40gm	0.50gm
8	Distilled water	q.s.	q.s.	q.s.
9	Rose water	q.s.	q.s.	q.s.

Apparatus:

There were several/various apparatus used which are as follows:

- Beaker
- China dish
- Measuring cylinder
- Glass rod
- Mixer/grinder
- Conical flask
- Burner
- Mortar and pestle

Instrument:

- Weighing balance
- pH paper
- Mixer
- Heating mantle

Chemical:

- Bees-wax
- Borax
- Liquid paraffin
- Methyl para

Procedure of cream:

Oily phase: Heat Bees wax, liquid paraffin in Petri dish at a temperature 75°C in water bath

Aqueous phase: Dissolve borax in a beaker add methyl paraben and distilled water.

Mix the all ingredients with continuous stirring. Heated 75°C. temperature. Transfer the aqueous phase into oily phase with continuous stirring and add aloe vera gel, Neem extract, cucumber and Tulsi extract in with continuous stirring and finally add rose oil.

Excipient and herbal ingredient used with their roles:

Table No 2: Excipients And Ingredient

Sr. No	Ingredients	Role
1	Turmaric	Anti-septic, anti inflammatory
2	Tulsi	Anti bacterial
3	Neem	Promote wound healing
4	Bee-wax	Emulsifying agent
5	Liquid paraffin	Lubricating agent
6	Borax	Alkaline agent
7	Methyl paeaben	Preservative
8	Distilled water	Veical
9	Rose water	Fragrance

7. Evaluation:**1. Physical parameters**

In this test color, odor, texture, and state of cream are observed.

Table No 3 : Physical Parameters

Sr. No	Parameters	F1C	F2C	F3C
1	Color	Faint yellow	Faint yellow	Faint yellow
2	Odor	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant
3	Texture	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth
4	State	Semi-solid	Semi-solid	Semi-solid

2. Irritancy Test

Mark the area (1 cm²) on the left-hand dorsal surface. Then the cream was applied to the area and etimenoted. After interval upto 24hr. it is checked for irritant effect, erythema and edema If any than reported.

Table No 4 : Irritancy Test

Sr. No	Formulation	Irritaneffect	Erythema	Edema
1	F1C	Nil	Nil	Nil
2	F2C	Nil	Nil	Nil
3	F3C	Nil	Nil	Nil

Irritancy: Mark the area (1 cm²) on the left-hand dorsal surface. Then the cream was applied to the area and the time noted. After interval up to 24 hr. it is checked for irritant effect, erythema and edema if any than reported

3. Washability Test:

Washability Test Was carried out by applying a small amount of cream on the hand an then washing it with help of tap water.All three formulations were easily washable.

Table No 5: Wash ability Test

Sr.No	Formulation	Washability
1	F1C	Easily washabl
2	F2C	Easily washabl
3	F3C	Easily washabl

4. **Phase separation Test:** Prepared cream is kept intightly closed container at room temperature away from sunlight and observed for 24 hours for phase.

Table No 6 : Phase separation

Sr. No	Formulation	Phase separation
1	F1C	No phase separation
2	F2C	No phase separation
3	F3C	No phase separation

5. **Spreadability Test :** Spread ability Is carried out for all three formulations that is, F1C,F2C and F3C.The less time take for the separation of both the slide better the spreadability. There for according to statement F2C had better spreadability .

Table No8: Spreadability Test

S.No	Formulation	Time (sec)	Spreadability(gcm/sec)
1	F1C	7	2.14
2	F2C	5	3
3	F3C	6	2.5

6. **pH Test:** Take 0.5 g of cream and dispersed it in 50 ml distilled water. Then check it's pH by using digital pH meter

Table No 9 : pH Test

Sr. no.	Formulation	pH
1	F1C	7.2
2	F2C	7.5
3	F3C	7.3

8. RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

All the three formulations F1H, F2H, F3H showed

good appearance, PH, adequate viscosity and no phase separation was observed. Also, the

formulations F1H, F2H, F3H showed no redness, erythema and irritation during irritancy study and they were easily washable. All the three formulations F1H, F2H, F3H were stable at room temperature.

Formulation can be detected in several ways in the physical appearances, color, and texture of the preparation.

9. Summary:

The cream was prepared by using the cream base that is bee's wax, liquid paraffin, borax, methylparaben, distilled water, Borax extracts of Turmeric,Neem and Tulsi. Homogenous mixing of all the excipients and the herbal extracts to formulate the cream, we have developed three batches of our herbal cream, namely F1H, F2H, and F3H. All three batches were evaluated for different parameters like appearance, PH, viscosity, phase separation.

10. CONCLUSION:

The uses of cream have been increased in many folds in personal care system. The uses bioactive ingredient in influence biological functions of skin and provide nutrients necessary for the healthy skin. The prepared formulation showed good spreadability, no evidence of phase separation and good consistency during the study period.

The prepared herbal cream has best properties and having nutritional values using less chemical which protects the skin from the various skin problem. Since the cream was prepared by using simple ingredients and simple method so the cream is also economical. The herbal cosmetic formulation is safe to use and it can be used as the provision of a barrier to protect skin. The result of different tests of cream showed that the formation could be used topically in order to protect skin against damage. Natural remedies are more acceptable in the belief that they are safer with fewer side effects than the synthetic ones. Further research will carry out to check scientifically the synergistic action of formulation.

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